

THE ROLE OF ENERGY IN THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *These days, the energy zone is the basis of the improvement of any country. Possibilities for economic improvement, cozy residing of the populace, schooling, scientific offerings, social safety, slight activity of communal economy are created in this location. But today, it is difficult to preserve the big energy infrastructure in operating order, and boom the extent of strength production without moving the enterprise to the path of market economic system. As political elements weigh in, Uzbekistan's financial issues take a secondary location in power device markets. This paper discusses the scope of opposition coverage within the Uzbekistan energetic industry. The authors emphasize on the outcomes of a passive opposition authority in organizing an aggressive energy marketplace.*

Keywords: *energy sector, economic development, energy infrastructure, alternative energy infrastructure, economic consideration, electricity industry.*

РОЛЬ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМ РАЗВИТИИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. *В наши дни энергетическая зона является основой благоустройства любой страны. В этом месте созданы возможности для экономического оздоровления, уютного проживания населения, школьного образования, научной деятельности, социальной защиты, небольшой деятельности коммунального хозяйства. Но сегодня трудно сохранить в рабочем состоянии крупную энергетическую инфраструктуру, увеличить масштабы производства прочности, не переводя предприятие на путь рыночной экономической системы. По мере влияния политических элементов финансовые вопросы Узбекистана отходят на второй план на рынках энергетического оборудования. В данной статье обсуждаются масштабы освещения оппозиции в энергетической отрасли Узбекистана. Авторы делают акцент на результатах пассивной оппозиционной власти в организации агрессивного энергетического рынка.*

Ключевые слова: *энергетика, экономическое развитие, энергетическая инфраструктура, инфраструктура альтернативной энергетики, экономическое рассмотрение, электроэнергетика.*

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is a vital component of a rustic's economic development. It is widely applied in agricultural and allied fields which include the manufacturing and shipping of fertilizers, pesticides, and farm equipment. it's miles vital for houses for cooking, lighting fixtures, and warmth. Coal, Petroleum, natural fuel, Uranium, and strength are all fuel substances that can be used to create power.

Over the last 3 a long time, many countries around the world liberalized their markets by regulatory reforms. The fashion closer to freer markets turned into specially wonderful in network industries. at the side of privatizations, the function of the market technique has turn out to be distinguished in these industries. even as there have been significant differences throughout

industry primarily based on marketplace laws creates situations for opposition, which allows to increase the performance of production, transportation, processing, and most importantly, to offer purchasers with natural gas constantly. It also lets in to attract no longer most effective finances, but additionally buyers with present day technology and enjoy to the implementation of tasks.

Impact on the economy by introducing "Automation and Digitization" into the energy system. Within the oil and gasoline industry, digitization is taken into consideration a key manner to growth the competitiveness and profitability of market family members. Nearly all technological techniques may be modeled earlier, as opposed to being instantaneous thru trial and blunders. A few hours of simulation replaces months of testing at the same time as presenting a more accurate illustration of formation traits. As a end result, years of labor might be saved, and oil production will increase by way of one and a half of to 2 instances. For example, with a view to make certain the introduction of cutting-edge statistics and communication technology and the automation of methods, together with the corporation "IKS preserving" in the energy zone, thinking of the contemporary and lengthy-term business goals of the enterprise, the "complicated and deliberate improvement concept of automation and digitalization of the gas and strength complex of the Republic of Uzbekistan" "is developing. This idea is presently being labored on. According with the choice of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 9, 2019 "On measures to provide the populace and the economic system with energy resources, financial recovery of the oil and gasoline network and enhance its control device" No. PQ-4388 working with international economic establishments a venture workplace became established. The involvement of worldwide specialists with great revel in in reforming the oil and fuel enterprise in unique countries is increasing year by year.

Nowadays, it remains an essential undertaking to completely modernize the device of strength stations, existing thermal energy plants and hydroelectric power vegetation - to introduce system and technology primarily based on the ultra-modern achievements within the area of strength performance. A clear example of this is the reality that steam-gas devices manufactured with the aid of main overseas groups are being set up in existing thermal power plants throughout the country. At the core of every such modernization is the work of hundreds of country wide and overseas specialists. Without their expert capabilities, it is not possible to put in force initiatives with accurate calculations and total existing situations, mainly, tasks that keep in mind both wellknown and specific aspects, from the operating time and potential of a positive IES. It can not be otherwise with a complicated technical facility like a energy plant.

Achieving economic efficiency by applying "digital technologies" to the energy sector. If the projects envisaged in the Investment Program, which can be intently related to virtual technology, are absolutely carried out, our united states of america will produce 21 billion kWh extra energy than in 2016. In addition, energy-saving technologies used in the modernization of present electricity plants and creation of new ones make it viable to reduce fuel costs via 1% consistent with 1 kW/h. As a end result, a mean of two billion cubic meters of natural gas is saved in the development of power.

In 2020 itself, the construction of six new power plants became began on the premise of public-non-public partnership with foreign investors. Their total cost is 2 billion dollars, and their overall ability is 2,700 megawatts.

Due to the implementation of virtual investment tasks in 2020, in 2021, 9 new electricity

plant life with a ability of 1,387 megawatts can be launched in our country. In the past two years, two solar power plants with a capacity of 100 MW each are planned to be put into operation (Total Eren (France) in Samarkand region, Masdar (UAE) in Navoi region are implementing their projects.

Measures to be implemented in the energy system to achieve economic efficiency.

The reforms accomplished in the oil and gas sector have to be focused on the result that ensures the pride of the growing desires of consumers for the products of the oil and gas industry, and ensures the balance of the economic interests of suppliers and consumers. Deliberating the forecast of herbal gas consumption accomplishing 56.5 billion cubic meters by 2030, the main challenge is to implement comprehensive measures to meet the growing demand.

DISCUSSION

For this, the following measures are taken:

- growing the electricity performance of the financial system by encouraging the usage of energy-saving technology, machines and gadget;
- to in addition develop the advent of marketplace mechanisms and create same situations for the implementation of commercial enterprise activities for all marketplace participants, irrespective of the shape of possession;
- through introducing revolutionary technologies, contemporary principles of company control, growing paintings performance within the fields of geological exploration, extraction, transportation, processing and sale of hydrocarbon raw materials;
- improvement of the base of hydrocarbon uncooked materials of branch businesses at the cost of sporting out geological-exploration works within the oil and fuel areas of the country;
- retaining the necessary volumes of hydrocarbon manufacturing by using introducing newly located and previously suspended deposits;

CONCLUSIONS

As we additionally need to speed up reforms within the strength zone of Uzbekistan, we need to enforce international experience, renew centers and devices which have already lived out their lives, appeal to overseas and nearby traders and noticeably reform the system. as an

instance. For example, in the country of Germany A clear example is that the economy is being improved as a result of the work being done. This country wide approach is being implemented through a massive number of countries. The energy sector is not a hotbed of corruption where large and small corruption is allowed in the system, or a source of corruption that feeds someone, it is a powerful industry that fully satisfies the needs of the whole country in this regard and benefits the economy of Uzbekistan. it's miles necessary to rotate.

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